

On the Consensus of General Mechanics with Cosmological Theory

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Abstract

This paper supplements my recent work titled "GENERAL MECHANICS" by exploring its implications for kinematics and dynamics[4]. We derive a new equation that offers an improved understanding of gravity, particularly in the context of black holes and dark matter. The results provide further insights into how general mechanics can unify these phenomena with established cosmological theories.

0.1 Introduction

The study of gravity has evolved significantly from the classical formulation provided by Newton to the complex interpretations offered by modern cosmology. Newton's law of universal gravitation successfully describes the motion of planets, moons, and other bodies under typical conditions, yet it faces significant limitations when applied to phenomena such as black holes and dark matter.

Dark matter, a form of matter that does not emit, absorb, or reflect light, presents one of the greatest mysteries in modern physics. Its existence is inferred from its gravitational effects on visible matter, yet its precise nature remains elusive. Standard gravitational models, including Newton's equation, cannot fully explain the rotational curves of galaxies without invoking the presence of dark matter. This discrepancy highlights the need for a more refined equation that can reconcile these observations with known physics.

Similarly, black holes—regions of spacetime with gravitational fields so intense that nothing, not even light, can escape—pose significant challenges for Newtonian gravity. The behavior of matter near black holes, particularly at their event horizons, defies classical mechanics. Newton's equation is inadequate for describing the extreme warping of spacetime that occurs in such environments, where relativistic effects become dominant.

This paper builds upon the framework of "General Mechanics" to propose a new approach for addressing these challenges. By deriving a modified equation for gravity, we aim to provide a more comprehensive understanding of both dark matter and black holes, integrating these concepts into a unified framework consistent with known physical theories. In doing so, we seek to bridge the gap between classical mechanics and the complexities of modern cosmology.

0.2 The Absolute Values

In "GENERAL MECHANICS," we introduced the concept of peculiar derivatives, which allow differentiation inside absolute values. These were denoted by $\frac{D}{Dx}$. For example:

$$\frac{D}{Dx} |\sin x| = |\cos x|$$

The reasoning behind this, as we will come to understand, is that time can approach zero but never reach it, and it cannot be negative. In simpler terms, this arises because gravity is symmetric.

0.3 Equation for Gravitational Acceleration

We can now derive an improved equation for gravitational acceleration using the theory of general mechanics. The visualization of space coordinates as dynamic is a translation of interpreting curved spacetime as linear. The key idea is that you can rotate a curved surface so that it appears flat. In this context, we are observing a region or angle where curved spacetime seems to be flat.

Figure 1: Figure 1 shows two instances of the same curved line; the second line is a rotated version of the first that appears straight.

If we allow a mass to move along the path at a constant velocity, and observe it from both perspectives, the mass will arrive the same distance over the same time on both lines. However, from the second perspective, the mass will appear to slow down in the region with a bump. We can now ask: what are the velocity and acceleration of the mass at any point on the line? This depends on the curvature of the line. After some trial and error, I found that the equation describing this relationship is:

$$y = |\rho e^{-kMr^2}|$$

where ρ is the density, M is the mass, and r is the distance from the mass. This is not the conventional curvature described in general relativity. Calculating $V(r)$ is straightforward:

$$dr^2 + |4\rho^2 k^2 r^2 M^2 e^{-kMr^2}| dr^2 = ds^2$$

$$V(r)^2 \left(1 + |4\rho^2 k^2 r^2 M^2 e^{-kMr^2}|\right) = c^2$$

$$V(r) = \frac{c}{\sqrt{1 + |4\rho^2 k^2 r^2 M^2 e^{-kMr^2}|}}$$

The acceleration $a(r)$ can be calculated as $a(r) = \frac{dV(r)}{dr} \cdot \frac{dr}{dt}$:

$$a(r) = 2k^2 M^2 c^2 \rho^2 \frac{(2|r| + 2r^3 k M) e^{-kMr^2}}{(1 + |4\rho^2 k^2 r^2 M^2 e^{-kMr^2}|)^2}$$

Newton's equation does not account for density, and this is why it provides incorrect answers at different scales. For black holes, by examining our equation for $V(r)$, it is evident that as density increases, $V(r)$ can only approach the speed of light but never reach it. This means that massless particles can escape, but it would take a very long time. The point is that black holes emit radiation, but the radiation takes a very long time to actually escape. Both density and mass play a crucial role in determining the strength of gravitational acceleration. For example, in the case of protons, the density is large, resulting in strong gravitational acceleration, but the mass is small, making its range very short. This is what is now known as the strong force. This same reasoning also explains why dark matter does not exist; the errors arise due to the lack of intricacy in Newton's equation.

Bibliography

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